

SHORT NOTES

A New Method for the Synthesis of 4-Hydroxy- and 4-Methoxy-homophthalic Acids

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4-Hydroxy-and/or 4-methoxy-homophthalic acids have been prepared by a number of methods: (i) from 6-methoxyhydrindone¹, obtained from *p*-methoxydihydrocinnamoyl chloride, (ii) from homophthalic acid² by nitration etc., (iii) from 6-methoxyphthalide³, prepared from *m*-methoxybenzoic acid by the method of Fritsch⁴. All these methods involved a number of steps and overall yields were very poor.

During our investigation on the synthesis of isocoumarins, we have found that 4-methoxyhomophthalic acid (IIIb) can be conveniently prepared in about 80% yield and 4-hydroxyhomophthalic acid (IIIa) in about 50% yield from *m*-methoxy- and *m*-hydroxy-benzoic acid respectively in three simple stages. *m*-Hydroxy- and *m*-methoxy-benzoic acids were condensed with chloral hydrate in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid according to Fritsch⁴ to provide the respective trichloromethylphthalides (I). These phthalides were reduced with zinc and acetic acid according to Hurry and Meldrum⁵ to furnish the respective 2-($\beta\beta$ -dichloroethyl)benzoic acid derivatives (II). These dichloro compounds were hydrolysed and oxidised to the corresponding homophthalic acids (III) by treating them with concentrated sulphuric acid (vide Meldrum and Kapadia⁶). The experimental procedures adopted by Fritsch⁴ and by Hurry and Meldrum⁵ were modified to obtain better yields.

[a: R=H.

b: R=Me]

1. Chakravarti and Swaminathan, *this Journal*, 1934, 11, 105.
2. Ungande *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1945, 10, 533.
3. Kantal *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 3377.
4. Fritsch, *Annalen*, 1897, 296, 344.
5. Hurry and Meldrum, *this Journal*, 1934, 11, 539.
6. Meldrum and Kapadia, *ibid.*, 1932, 9, 483.

Various other nuclear substituted homophthalic acids can be synthesised from appropriately substituted benzoic acids by using this method. Further work in this direction is in progress and the results will be published in due course.

3-Trichloromethyl-6-methoxyphthalide (Ib).—*m*-Methoxybenzoic acid (12.5 g.), chloral hydrate (16 g.), and H_2SO_4 (38 ml, 95%) were mixed, shaken well, and left at room temperature for about 24 hours. It was then poured on crushed ice, the product separating was triturated with sodium bicarbonate solution, washed well with water, and dried; m.p. 130-32°, yield 24 g. (it was quite pure). It crystallised from acetic acid in needles, m.p. 136-37° (Fritsch⁴ record; m.p. 135°).

2-($\beta\beta$ -Dichloroethyl)-5-methoxybenzoic Acid (IIb).—To the phthalide (Ib) (19 g.), dissolved in glacial acetic acid (140 ml) and mechanically stirred, zinc dust (15 g.) was added in small portions during 1½ hrs. at room temperature when heat was liberated. Stirring was continued for about half an hour after the addition was complete; it was then just heated on a water bath and filtered hot from zinc acetate. The filtrate was diluted with water and the solid separating was washed well with water and dried; m.p. 162-64°, yield 14 g. (it is sufficiently pure). It crystallised from dilute methanol as prismatic rods, m.p. 167-68° (Hurry and Meldrum⁵ report m.p. 165°).

4-Methoxyhomophthalic Acid (IIIb).—The dichloro compound (IIb) (7 g.) was added in small lots to H_2SO_4 (14 ml, 90%) with constant shaking. The mixture, protected from moisture, was occasionally heated on a water bath. The addition of the dichloro compound was so adjusted that the second lot was added only after the first lot had dissolved completely. The mixture turned pasty at the end of the reaction. Further H_2SO_4 (6 ml) was then added and the mixture heated on the water bath till no more HCl evolved (~ 2hrs.). It was poured on crushed ice (60 g.), the solid product washed well with cold water, and dried; m.p. 180-82°, yield 5.5 g. It crystallised from water as shining prismatic plates, m.p. 186-87°, yield 5 g. (Chakravarti *et al.*¹ report m.p. 188° and Ungande *et al.*², m.p. 185-86°).

3-Trichloromethyl-6-hydroxyphthalide (Ia).—*m*-Hydroxybenzoic acid (5 g.), chloral hydrate (6 g.), and H_2SO_4 (15 ml, 95%) were mixed and shaken well. After keeping the reaction mixture at room temperature for about 48 hours, it was worked up as in the case of (Ib); m.p. 195-97°, yield 7.5 g. (quite pure). It crystallised from acetic acid as prismatic needles, m.p. 199-200° (Fritsch⁴ reports m.p. 197-98°).

2-($\beta\beta$ -Dichloroethyl)-5-hydroxybenzoic Acid (IIa) was prepared by reduction of⁶ (Ia) (10 g.) with zinc dust (7.5 g.) and glacial acetic acid (70 ml), as in the case of (IIb); m.p. 189-90°, yield 7g. It crystallised from dilute methanol as needles, m.p. 196-97° (Hurry and Meldrum⁵ report m.p. 194°).

4-Hydroxyhomophthalic acid (IIIa) was prepared from (IIa) (3 g.) and H_2SO_4 (7 ml, 90%) as in the case of (IIIb); m.p. 211-12° (decomp.), yield 2g. It crystallised from water as shining plates, m.p. 216-17°. (decomp.) (Ungande *et al.*² report m.p. 214-15° decomp.).

Methyl Ether of (IIIa) was prepared by methylating (IIIa) with dimethyl sulphate according to Ungande *et al.*²; m.p. and mixed m.p. with (IIIb) obtained before, 186-87°.